

Air purifiers in classrooms for infection control: a pilot study *(study protocol)*

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Cathinka Halle Julin¹, Runar Barstad Solberg¹, Ingeborg Hess Elgersma¹, Petter Elstrøm¹, Christine Holst¹, Arnfinn Helleve^{1,3}, Unni Gopinathan¹, Atle Fretheim^{1,2}, Sverre B. Holøs⁴.

Affiliations

¹Centre for Epidemic Interventions Research (CEIR), Norwegian Institute of Public Health

²Faculty of Health Sciences, Oslo Metropolitan University

³Centre for Evaluation of Public Health Measures, Norwegian Institute of Public Health

⁴SINTEF, Norway

Abstract

Background

During the COVID-19 pandemic, school closures were implemented to safeguard students, teachers, and their families from the airborne transmission of SARS-CoV-2. However, these closures brought potential issues of disrupted learning, social isolation, and well-being challenges, highlighting the need for alternative measures. This pilot study aims to explore the feasibility and potential impact of integrating air purifiers into classrooms to enhance infection control.

Objective

The primary objective is to assess the acceptability and feasibility of deploying air purifiers equipped with HEPA filters in classroom environments. We will compare the efficiency of ceiling-mounted versus portable air purifiers on air quality, to guide further investigations. Further, we will explore various outcome measures and determine the viability and value of conducting a larger randomized trial.

Method

The first part of this study involves five classrooms in five schools, where two will be equipped with ceiling-mounted and three with portable air purifiers. All will receive air quality sensors. We will engage educators to evaluate the practicality of implementing these measures, by conducting interviews and observations. The second part will involve three classrooms from one school, where ceiling-mounted and portable air purifiers will be alternated over six weeks to assess their efficacy in real-world conditions. We will collect data on airborne particle levels and overall air quality.

Expected Results

This pilot study aims to provide insights into the feasibility of using air purifiers for infection control in classrooms, and the effect of air purifiers on air quality in a real-world setting. Moreover, stakeholder perspectives gathered through interviews will provide valuable insights into the acceptability and feasibility of such interventions. Ultimately, the results will lay the groundwork for larger-scale trials and potential policy recommendations, steering efforts to safeguard the well-being of students, educators, and the broader community within educational settings.

Background

SARS-CoV-2 is an airborne pathogen that primarily transmits from human-to-human through droplets and aerosol [1]. The rapid spread of SARS-CoV-2 across borders culminated in the COVID-19 pandemic and resulted in severe disruptions of everyday life worldwide. Among the many public health and social measures enacted to protect people from COVID-19 disease, school closure was one of the first implemented.

By April 2020, partial or full school closure had been mandated by governments in over 180 countries [2]. School closure, while ambiguous regarding the effectiveness on transmission of SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19 incidence, and mortality [3], has been associated with several negative effects, such as learning loss and increased mental health problems [3-6]. Thus, school closures were radical because it entailed a dramatic deprivation of essential educational and interpersonal engagement for children and adolescents [3]. Furthermore, it was a costly intervention due to the burden imposed on parents and caregivers, as it required parents and caregivers to often take time off work [7, 8]. Therefore, the decision to close schools should be weighed carefully against these potential harms. It is crucial to explore alternative measures that can keep schools open while minimizing the risk of disease transmission, ensuring the safety of both students and teachers.

In this context, international assessments of the COVID-19 response, such as the Lancet Covid-19 Commission, have identified improved ventilation and air cleaning as promising interventions for avoiding school closures [9]. This measure is particularly pertinent given that schools are high-risk settings for the spread of respiratory tract infections due to the extended time that students spend in crowded and often inadequately ventilated spaces [10-13]. In Norway, 35% of teachers in lower and secondary schools report unsatisfactory indoor climate caused by poor indoor ventilation in classrooms. Despite this, air cleaning has received little attention as an approach to infection control in Norway compared to other European countries. This oversight is concerning, especially since The Lancet COVID-19 commission also highlights several other benefits from improving air quality in schools, such as increased test scores, better cognitive functions, reduced asthma symptoms and reduction in child absenteeism [9].

A notable intervention gaining attention in both political and academic discussions is the use of air purifiers with high-efficiency particulate air (HEPA) filters [10, 12, 14-18]. Such HEPA purifiers must adhere to strict standards, filtering at least 99.7% of aerosols particles with a diameter of 0.15 or larger. A recent systematic review of experimental studies provide evidence for HEPA filter's potential to eliminate airborne SARS-CoV-2 [17]. Furthermore, HEPA filters could also be useful beyond SARS-CoV-2 and other respiratory viruses as they capture larger airborne particles such as pollen or outdoor pollutants [18]. However, the literature documenting the effectiveness and potential harms of air purifiers with HEPA filter on indoor air quality and mitigation of infection transmission in school settings is limited.

A recent retrospective cohort study from Italy showed that students in classrooms with mechanical ventilation reduced the risk of SARS-CoV-2 infection with 74% [19]. As air purifiers with HEPA filters are even more efficient in reducing particle concentrations [20] they could potentially have an even greater impact on transmission of airborne viruses. One randomized trial reported a 45% improvement in indoor air quality in a classroom with HEPA filters as compared to an untreated classroom, but they did not report effects on seasonal viral illnesses [21]. Similar results have been reported in another study where HEPA filters significantly reduced concentration of outdoor pollution in the classroom [18]. While installing HEPA filters in classrooms can reduce aerosol density, and consequently potentially lower viral transmission risk and absenteeism, there are potential risks and disadvantages.

These include additional costs, noise, draught, energy consumption, and extra care that must be taken to replace and dispose of the filters [13].

In some countries, the authorities recommend using air purifiers e.g. in classrooms, to reduce the spread of SARS-CoV-2 virus: The Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) in the USA encourages schools to “Consider portable air cleaners that filters to enhance air cleaning wherever possible” [22]. In Germany, the Bavarian government recently allocated 190 million Euro for installment of air filters in classrooms [23]. In England, the National Institute of Health and Research has awarded £ 2.3 million for the conduct of a trial of air purifiers in care homes [24], and a trial of air purifiers in classrooms is also reported to be in the pipeline [25, 26].

Rationale for the proposed study

The potential impact of air purifiers in schools, hinges on multiple factors, including the presence of effective mechanical ventilation systems, local environment, classroom size, and student count. An intervention trial where schools are randomly assigned to receive cost-free air purifier installations, is thus needed to enable an unconfounded comparison of schools with and without air purifiers. However, conducting such a study with a sufficient number of schools to yield reliable results is a significant undertaking. We therefore aim to first conduct a small pilot study to evaluate the feasibility and acceptability of installing and running air purifiers in schools, to lay the grounds for a larger trial.

Additionally, this pilot study will provide an initial evaluation of the effectiveness of air purifiers in reducing particulate matter within classroom environments. From the literature, we know that the HEPA filters in air purifiers are capable of filtering viruses from the air. However, our measurement tools cannot detect viral particles in the air. We can, however, measure larger particles. If a reduction in viral particles is to be expected, a corresponding decrease in larger particles should be observable with the use of air purifiers in classrooms. If we do not observe a significant reduction in these larger particles, it would suggest that it is unlikely for the classroom air purifiers to remove a sufficient proportion of airborne viruses to reduce the risk of viral transmission.

Risks and benefits

A key motivation for this pilot study is to identify unforeseen negative consequences of placing air purifiers in classrooms. However, it seems likely that installing air purifiers, which are widely used in many countries, poses minimal, if any, health risks for the teachers and students. On the contrary, there is increasing evidence showing great benefits of good ventilation and improved indoor air quality – such as protecting children’s health and enhancing learning [27]. Apart from the slight noise from the air purifiers, and their uptake of space in the classroom, we do not expect negative consequences for the students or teachers. However, interviews with both students and teachers will be conducted during the intervention period to capture any negative experiences.

A general concern when implementing RCTs in an educational setting is the risk of compromising educational quality or introducing unfair differences between intervention and control groups [28]. In this pilot study, we will explore how the intervention can be implemented with minimal disruption of the teaching environment. Students and teachers are central end-users in this study. Engaging representatives of these groups as co-researchers is important for several reasons [29]. For instance, involving young people in research can increase relevance of the research agenda, increase recruitment of research participants, provide more insightful data, as well as raise the ethical standards [30]. In this study, the students and teachers will be engaged through interviews and questionnaires.

Finally, the air purifiers are designed to operate without significant maintenance, ensuring that teachers do not need to invest time and effort in their upkeep. Further, we plan to use automated timers to turn the purifiers on and off, further reducing the workload on teachers.

Study aim

The aims of this pilot study are two-fold:

- 1) To assess the feasibility and acceptability of conducting a comprehensive trial of air purifiers in classroom settings, including unforeseen negative aspects.
- 2) To perform an initial evaluation of the effectiveness of air purifiers in improving air quality.

Research design and methods

Overview of study design

The pilot study will consist of two parts, each lasting approximately 2 months in the winter of 2024. The outcomes of this study will further inform and shape the implementation of the main trial, which will be described in a separate protocol.

In part 1, we will evaluate feasibility and acceptability of conducting a study on air purifiers in Norwegian classrooms during a study period of 6 weeks. We will explore the practicalities, as well as the teacher's experiences of the implementation of air purifiers and air quality sensors in classroom settings. We will further explore the process of data collection for outcome measurements and gather data on the effect of purifiers on air quality to support the findings from Part 2 (below). Four schools will be recruited to join this part of the study, each providing one classroom for the study.

In part 2, we will evaluate the direct effect of air purifiers on air quality, including a comparison of the effect of ceiling mounted and portable air purifiers during a period of 6 weeks. One school will be recruited to join this part of the study. They will need to provide three classrooms in the same building, and the classrooms should preferably exhibit average to poor air quality.

Schools and recruitment

Both primary schools, secondary schools, and high schools could have been suitable locations for conducting the study. However, students in secondary schools and high schools typically use a variety of different classrooms throughout the day more so than students in primary schools. This means that they would spend a larger portion of the school day in classrooms that do not have air purifiers if they were to be included in the study. Time spent in classrooms without air purifiers may reduce our ability to demonstrate an effect of the air purifiers. Furthermore, it is likely that older students spend more time in larger groups outside of school hours, such as at social gatherings or parties, where the risk of transmission is higher. This makes the primary school the most suitable place for conducting such a study and being able to demonstrate an effect of the intervention.

We will therefore invite primary schools in Eastern Norway for the participation in this pilot study. The preference will be to include 7th-grade classrooms, as 7th grade will be the target group in the main trial. However, if the school administration or the study group finds it more suitable for this pilot study, classrooms from the 5th or 6th grade classrooms may also be included. The considerations will include the placement of classrooms, the regularity of use of the classrooms during the study period, among other factors.

The decision to target 5th to 7th graders rather than 1st to 4th grades, stems from the consideration of after-school programs ("Aktivitetsskole" or "Skolefritidsordning") which is typically used by 1st to 4th grade students in Norway. In these programs, students frequently utilize different rooms than their

regular classrooms. Since we cannot install air cleaning devices in these extra rooms, the time that 1st to 4th graders would spend together in these spaces each day would lessen the impact of the intervention. Moreover, we assume that schools could be more focused on recording absences during this last year of primary education, which could potentially work to our advantage when gathering these data. The pilot study will consequently primarily target the 7th grade.

For part 2 of the study, we may also include other grades as we are mostly interested in the effect of the purifiers on particulate matter numbers, and not as much the acceptability and feasibility in a primary school classroom setting.

Interventions

Part 1

Two classrooms will be equipped with ceiling-mounted air purifiers, while the other three will get portable air purifiers. The decision to include one extra school is to provide ensure a sufficient sample in case one school chooses to drop out (originally, we planned for four schools in part 1). All five classrooms will have air quality sensors installed. Week 0 will involve installing and testing both purifiers and air sensors, and we will collect baseline measurements of air quality for each classroom. For the subsequent six weeks (Week 1–6, i.e. the study period), the air purifiers will be active in parallel with regular air quality monitoring (Figure 1). Additionally, air quality measurements will be taken in the week following the study period, to augment the baseline data. We will set the level of the air purifier at an acceptable level (intensity) for the teachers at the onset of the study period, but allow the teachers to adjust it further if preferred.

To collect more data on the effect of air purification on particulate matter count, the air purifiers will be turned off one day a week.

Part 2

All three classrooms will be equipped with both ceiling-mounted and portable air purifiers, as well as indoor air quality sensors. Week 0 will involve installing and testing both purifiers and sensors. For the subsequent six weeks (Week 1–6), the three classrooms will alternate weekly whether they have the ceiling-mounted, portable, or no air purifier, running (Figure 1). Baseline measurements will be taken as for part 1, described above. The level of the air cleaners will be determined based on acceptability and preliminary air quality measurement results from part 1. We will randomize the three classrooms to different orders of having ceiling-mounted, portable, or no air purifier running.

Data collection

Part 1

Interviews

Throughout the 6 week-long study period, we will engage with teachers and possibly selected study administration for brief interviews (we may use focus groups). The goal is to explore the feasibility and acceptability of running air purifiers in the classrooms. Up to 20 interviews will be performed, primarily at the outset of the intervention period and after the last week (Appendix 7 - interview guide). Ad hoc phone calls with teachers during the study period may also be performed. We will also ask students and their guardians to participate in brief interviews or focus groups at the end of the study periods, to capture their experiences with having the purifiers in their classrooms.

Observations and air quality measurements

The study team will visit the classrooms at various times during the study to observe the placement and use of the air purifiers. Particulate matter number concentration corresponding to PM_{2.5} will be

monitored at 5-minute intervals with optical sensors, along with CO₂ concentration, air temperature and air humidity in all classrooms. Volatile organic compounds (VOC) may also be monitored.

We will also encourage teachers to take part in observing and reporting to the study team examples of events related to having air purifiers in the classroom. This can consist of text messages, pictures, or short phone calls.

Absence data

We will interact with all schools to explore their procedures and systems for absence registration. We will further explore systematic methods for collecting these diverse types of information for the study, either directly from the schools or from the municipality. The absence data will be collected at group level only.

Questionnaires

We will evaluate the feasibility of recruiting teachers to answer questionnaires. They will be invited to answer questions in the beginning, during the study and at the end of the intervention. This will allow us to user test these questionnaires.

We will also evaluate the feasibility of inviting children and their parents to answer questionnaires to report absence, as well as reasons for absence throughout the study period. As an incentive for taking part, the children will have the opportunity to win small prizes through a prize drawing. We will send reminders to those who have not completed the baseline or end-of-follow up surveys.

We will use the following questionnaires:

1) Baseline survey to teachers on air quality and related symptoms

We will use a battery of questions from a modified MM 040 questionnaire. This questionnaire has been used in a number of studies and has also been translated to Norwegian. It will allow us to collect baseline data on potential benefits or harms with having an air purifier placed at the workplace.

2) Weekly survey to teachers on absence and reasons for absence

We will collect information about absence and reasons for absence (i.e. non-health associated, illness associated, etc) on a weekly basis, using a short survey, that will only take a few minutes to respond.

3) End survey to teachers

Similar questions from the MM040 questionnaire will be used.

4) Baseline survey for students/their guardians on absence and reasons for absence

We will collect information about school, class, gender, absence and reasons for absence (i.e. non-health associated, illness associated, etc) using a short survey, that will only take a few minutes to respond.

5) Weekly survey to students/their guardians on absence and reasons for absence

We will collect information about absence and reasons for absence (i.e. non-health associated, illness associated, etc) using a short survey, that will only take a few minutes to respond.

6) End survey to students.

In addition to the questions in the weekly survey, we will also ask about the acceptability of performing covid-19 tests in a similar study, as well as their preferred means of such testing.

Part 2

Particle number concentration corresponding to PM_{2,5} will be monitored at 5-minute intervals with optical sensors, along with CO₂ concentration, air temperature and air humidity at one location in all classrooms. Volatile organic compounds (VOC) may also be monitored. The same parameters will be monitored in ambient air and in the air supplied by the mechanical ventilation system. Monitoring will take place during the complete 6-week period.

The monitored data will be supplemented by a single-day measurement campaign where particle numbers in different size fractions (0.3-2.5, 2.5-5 and >5 µm) are measured with optical particle counters in ambient air, supply air and room air. Simultaneously particle number concentration will be monitored at multiple locations in selected rooms. Each classroom will be measured for a single day for each intervention (air purifiers off, ceiling-mounted purifier on, floor-standing purifier on).

Experiences with feasibility and acceptability will also be gathered through phone interviews of focus groups with teachers, adding to the data from part 1.

Study outcomes

Primary outcomes

- 1) Feasibility and acceptability of installing and running air purifiers in classrooms and of measuring air quality.
 - a. **Data source:** Interviews with teachers and students in part 1, supplemented with data from part 2.
- 2) Effectiveness of ceiling mounted versus portable air purifiers on improving air quality in classrooms.
 - a. **Data source:** Air quality measurements primarily from part 2 schools, supported by measurements from part 1 schools.
- 3) Feasibility of collecting absence data from different schools based on their registration system (digital/manual/etc.), or from the municipality's systems.
 - a. **Data source:** Experiences primarily from part 1 schools.

Secondary outcomes:

- 1) Feasibility of recruiting teachers to answer relevant surveys.
 - a. **Data source:** Experiences from part 1 schools.
- 2) Feasibility of recruiting students/their guardians to answer relevant surveys.
 - a. **Data source:** Experiences from part 1 schools.
- 3) Effect of air purifiers on perceived air quality (preliminary data)
 - a. **Data source:** Baseline and end survey for teachers.

Other outcomes

- 1) Proportion of absence due to respiratory disease.
 - a. **Data source:** Answers to survey from teachers and students.
- 2) Acceptability of using rapid tests or PCR tests to detect cases of covid-19 among students.
 - a. **Data source:** Answers to survey from students.

Sample size

As part 1 of this pilot is a feasibility and acceptability study, no sample size calculations were performed. However, as the feasibility and acceptability may differ between schools, we will aim to include five different schools for this part.

Part 2 will evaluate the effect of ceiling-mounted and portable air purifiers and compare their effectiveness in reducing particle density in the classroom air. As choosing portable air purifiers might be more ideal for a trial setting given both costs and feasibility of the installment, we will perform a non-inferiority study when comparing these types. We set a non-inferior margin and state that the portable is as good as the ceiling-mounted if there is a non-significant difference of 10 percentage points in particle density. For these calculations, particle density without air purification is assumed to be 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ [31]. Assuming that the ceiling mounted purifier removes 50%, and the portable removes 45%, the measured particle density after purification is 5 and 5.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. Given these assumptions, and a one-sided power calculation, we will need 28 measurements in each group. Thus, we will run part 2 of the trial for 6 weeks, measuring at least once daily in each classroom during the weekdays when the classrooms are in use, to get 30 measurements.

Figure 1: Study design of the pilot study. Part 1, exploring feasibility of installing and running air purifiers and sensors in classrooms in 4 different schools (A-E), is shown in the upper panel. Part 2, comparing the effect of ceiling mounted versus portable purifiers on air quality, in 3 parallel classrooms (1-3) in one school, is shown in the lower panel.

Air purifier devices

Specifications

Considering the probable importance of other pathways of virus dispersal than classroom air, we aim to achieve a 50 % reduction of indoor generated airborne particles containing active virus in the size range 1-10 μ m aerodynamic diameter. Since such particles are removed also by sedimentation, and viruses become deactivated in the environment, the clean air delivery rate (CADR) necessary to achieve a 50 % reduction depends on the actual ventilation rate and the deposition and deactivation rate of infectious agents.

The nominal CADR of the installed air purifiers will be > 700 m³/h. Assuming classrooms of 60 m² floor area and 180 m³ volumes used by 20 students, ventilated according to building code requirements and the deposition and inactivation rates of 0.3 and 0.36 suggested in REHVA Covid calculator, approximately 50 % reduction can be achieved. In classrooms with higher or lower ventilation rates, smaller and larger reductions will result.

Air purifiers deployed in the study will be using mechanical filtration (HEPA filters) capable of removing > 99,5 % of the most penetrating particle size from the air current passing the filter. Ozon production will not be at detectable levels, and operation shall be able to comply with class C in NS 8175: 2019 ($L_{p, A, T} \leq 35$ dB). During the pilot study, the number and physical placement of air purifiers and air quality monitors in individual classrooms will be decided upon after initial survey of the layout and ventilation characteristics of each room.

Type of air purifiers

Ceiling-mounted air purifiers have the advantage of not taking up floor space and will thus not stand in the way for the students and teachers. Further, they may be more efficient in distributing clean air evenly throughout a room and may be quieter than portable units. On the other side, they need professional setup and potentially integration with existing systems, which may be expensive. Also, unit costs are higher than for portable units.

Portable air purifiers are generally more affordable, and do not require professional installation or modification to existing systems. They can be easily moved around and easily accessed for maintenance and filter replacements. Disadvantages are their occupancy of floor space, and the accessibility which may attract curious students to temper with the air purifiers. Moreover, they provide more localized air quality improvements, and more units may be needed for larger classrooms. Maintenance may also be more frequent than for ceiling-mounted purifiers.

As ceiling-mounted and portable air purifiers each have their own set of advantages and disadvantages, the effectiveness, feasibility, and acceptability of both types will be explored in this pilot study.

Consent

It is not feasible to seek consent from each individual teacher, student and/or legal guardian for installation and running of portable air purifiers in the schools. Therefore, we will leave it entirely at the discretion of those responsible at each school to accept the offer of having air purifiers installed, or not. Absence data from the schools will be collected at group level only and will not need consent as these data will not be person identifiable.

However, for the sub studies where teachers and students will be asked to answer questionnaires and participate in interviews, individual consent will be gathered. Means and feasibility of collecting these individual consents will be explored in the pilot study, such as by paper consents distributed by

the teacher or electronic consents distributed through the school systems. We will only ask for consent from students in the schools in part 1 of the study, but from teachers in both part 1 and 2.

Timeline

Table 1: Timeline of study activities

Activity	Prep.	Intervention Period Weeks							
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Communicate with and recruit schools	X								
Explore absence registration systems		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Recruit teachers for questionnaires and interviews	X	X	X						
Recruit students for questionnaires and interviews		X	X	X					
Install and test air purifiers and sensors	X	X							
Intervention – feasibility/acceptability (part 1)									
Run ceiling or portable air purifiers: School A, B, C, D, E			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Intervention – effect of purifiers (part 2)									
Run ceiling air purifier: School F, classroom 1			X			X			
Run ceiling air purifier: School F, classroom 2				X			X		
Run ceiling air purifier: School F, classroom 3					X			X	
Run portable air purifier: School F, classroom 1					X			X	
Run portable air purifier: School F, classroom 2			X			X			
Run portable air purifier: School F, classroom 3				X			X		
Air quality measurements		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Short term air quality measurement campaign				X	X	X			
Phone/teams interviews with teachers/selected school personnel			X		(X)	(X)		X	X
Phone/teams interviews with students								X	X
Surveys for teachers (only part 1 schools)									
Baseline survey: Modified MM 040			X						
Weekly survey: Absence and symptoms				X	X	X	X		
End survey: Modified MM 040									X
Surveys for students (only part 1 schools)									
Baseline survey: Absence and reasons			X						
Weekly survey: Absence and reasons				X	X	X	X		
End survey: Absence and reasons, covid-19 testing									X

Statistical methods

We will provide details of the statistical analysis in the statistical analysis plan before the analyses are conducted.

Ethics

We have sought ethical approval for conducting the trial from the Regional Ethics Committee. The study was deemed to fall outside of the scope of the Health Research Law because it did not aim to procure new knowledge of illness and health (reference #656196). We assess the risk of negative consequences for pupils and school staff to be very small.

Data protection

Participant data will be stored in University of Oslo secure storage of research data (TSD). Survey data collected during the trial will automatically be transferred to TSD. All data used for the primary outcomes will be anonymous and/or aggregated, i.e. non-identifiable.

Funding

The funding of the project is not finalized, but most costs will be borne by CEIR – Centre for Epidemic Interventions Research at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health.

Dissemination of results

Results will be disseminated through conventional scientific channels (pre-print, scientific publication with open access), and media coverage. The trial will be registered in all relevant study registries.

Declaration of interests

We declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Ehsanifar, M., *Airborne aerosols particles and COVID-19 transition*. Environ Res, 2021. **200**: p. 111752.
2. Lee, J., *Mental health effects of school closures during COVID-19*. Lancet Child Adolesc Health, 2020. **4**(6): p. 421.
3. Samuel, H., B. Samuel Robert, and M. Kamal Ram, *School closures during COVID-19: an overview of systematic reviews*. BMJ Evidence-Based Medicine, 2023. **28**(3): p. 164.
4. Hammerstein, S., C. König, T. Dreisörner, and A. Frey, *Effects of COVID-19-Related School Closures on Student Achievement—A Systematic Review*. Front Psychol, 2021. **12**: p. 746289.
5. Mazrekaj, D. and K. De Witte, *The Impact of School Closures on Learning and Mental Health of Children: Lessons From the COVID-19 Pandemic*. Perspectives on Psychological Science. **0**(0): p. 17456916231181108.
6. Ortega Pacheco, Y.J. and V.I. Barrero Toncel, *The impact of school closure on children's well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic*. Asian J Psychiatr, 2022. **67**: p. 102957.
7. Kim, S.-J., et al., *Parental Mental Health and Children's Behaviors and Media Usage during COVID-19-Related School Closures*. jkms, 2021. **36**(25): p. e184-0.
8. Power, K., *The COVID-19 pandemic has increased the care burden of women and families*. Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy, 2020. **16**(1): p. 67-73.
9. Sachs, J.D., et al., *The Lancet Commission on lessons for the future from the COVID-19 pandemic*. The Lancet, 2022. **400**(10359): p. 1224-1280.
10. Curtius, J., M. Granzin, and J. Schrod, *Testing mobile air purifiers in a school classroom: Reducing the airborne transmission risk for SARS-CoV-2*. Aerosol Science and Technology, 2021. **55**(5): p. 586-599.
11. Falkenberg, T., et al., *Effect of portable HEPA filters on COVID-19 period prevalence: an observational quasi-interventional study in German kindergartens*. BMJ Open, 2023. **13**(7): p. e072284.
12. Fernández de Mera, I.G., et al., *HEPA filters of portable air cleaners as a tool for the surveillance of SARS-CoV-2*. Indoor Air, 2022. **32**(9): p. e13109.
13. Villers, J., et al., *SARS-CoV-2 aerosol transmission in schools: the effectiveness of different interventions*. Swiss Medical Weekly, 2022. **152**(2122): p. w30178.
14. Asanati, K., L. Voden, and A. Majeed, *Healthier schools during the COVID-19 pandemic: ventilation, testing and vaccination*. Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine, 2021. **114**(4): p. 160-163.
15. Azevedo, A., et al., *Effects of portable air cleaners and A/C unit fans on classroom concentrations of particulate matter in a non-urban elementary school*. PLOS ONE, 2022. **17**(12): p. e0278046.
16. Coyle, J.P., et al., *Efficacy of Ventilation, HEPA Air Cleaners, Universal Masking, and Physical Distancing for Reducing Exposure to Simulated Exhaled Aerosols in a Meeting Room*. Viruses, 2021. **13**(12): p. 2536.
17. Liu, D.T., et al., *Portable HEPA Purifiers to Eliminate Airborne SARS-CoV-2: A Systematic Review*. Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg, 2022. **166**(4): p. 615-622.
18. Nancy, C., et al., *Indoor Air Quality Intervention in Schools; Effectiveness of a Portable HEPA Filter Deployment in Five Schools Impacted by Roadway and Aircraft Pollution Sources*. medRxiv, 2022: p. 2022.01.12.22269175.
19. Buonanno, G., L. Ricolfi, L. Morawska, and L. Stabile, *Increasing ventilation reduces SARS-CoV-2 airborne transmission in schools: A retrospective cohort study in Italy's Marche region*. Frontiers in Public Health, 2022. **10**.
20. Liu, D.T., et al., *Portable HEPA Purifiers to Eliminate Airborne SARS-CoV-2: A Systematic Review*. Otolaryngology—Head and Neck Surgery, 2021. **166**(4): p. 615-622.

21. Phipatanakul, W., et al., *Effect of School Integrated Pest Management or Classroom Air Filter Purifiers on Asthma Symptoms in Students With Active Asthma: A Randomized Clinical Trial*. *Jama*, 2021. **326**(9): p. 839-850.
22. *Ventilation in Schools and Childcare Programs*. 2021 [cited 2021 20.09.2021]; Available from: <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/community/schools-childcare/ventilation.html>.
23. *Pressemitteilungen. Bericht aus der Kabinettssitzung vom 6. Juli 2021*. 2021 [cited 2021 20.09.2021]; Available from: <https://www.bayern.de/bericht-aus-der-kabinettssitzung-vom-6-juli-2021/>.
24. *Research Award: Air Filtration to reduce Respiratory Infections (including COVID-19) in care homes: the AFRI-c cluster randomised controlled trial with nested internal pilot, process and economic evaluations*. 2021 [cited 2021 20.09.2021]; Available from: <https://fundingawards.nihr.ac.uk/award/NIHR129783>.
25. *Covid: Air purifier and UV light pilot to combat school virus spread*. 2021 [cited 2021 20.09.2021]; Available from: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-england-leeds-58190189>.
26. Blueair. *The benefits of clean air in schools: A survey of teachers in London schools*. 2018.
27. Wargocki, P., J.A. Porras-Salazar, S. Contreras-Espinoza, and W. Bahnfleth, *The relationships between classroom air quality and children's performance in school*. *Building and Environment*, 2020. **173**: p. 106749.
28. Opheim, J.B.-M.V. *Hjelp, forskerne kommer! Erfaringer med randomisert kontrollert studie i småskolen*. 2022; Available from: <https://www.utdanningsnytt.no/bedre-skole-fagartikkel-forskning/hjelp-forskere-kommer-erfaringer-med-randomisert-kontrollert-studie-i-smaskolen/317833>.
29. Slattery, P., A.K. Saeri, and P. Bragge, *Research co-design in health: a rapid overview of reviews*. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 2020. **18**(1): p. 17.
30. Wilson, O., et al., *A rapid evidence review of young people's involvement in health research*. London: Wellcome, 2020. **3**.
31. Rune Becher, M.B., Finn Martinsen, Johan Øvrevik, *Indoor Climate in Schools and Kindergartens: Health Implications for Children and Adolescents*. , Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Editor. 2016.